

Longitudinal and Cross-Sectional Analysis of Greenhouse Gas Emissions from the Energy Sector: A Python-Based Look for the Period 1990-2022

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Abstract: Since the publication of the 5th Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and the signing of the Paris Agreement, significant efforts have been made to analyse greenhouse gas emissions from all human activity, mainly from the energy sector, which allows for the assessment of appropriate policies for their reduction. Among these policies is that of bringing energy in an accessible and safe manner to a greater number of people by moving to generation sources with lower environmental impacts. Within this framework, the company Bp has published its reports related to global statistics on the production and consumption of energy in this sector for 71 editions. Additionally, starting with the 1990 edition, it has included GHG emissions. This research work is carried out with the purpose of analysing emissions from 1990 to 2022. Using the Python program, a longitudinal analysis is carried out for the period from 1990 to 2022 of global emissions, by continent and the top 5 countries. Subsequently, the emissions of countries classified in quartiles and in a transversal manner are analysed in the years 1990, 2000, 2010, 2015 and 2022. This study provides a reference framework on the efficiency of the energy policies established to achieve the goals of the Paris Agreement.

Keywords: Greenhouse gas emissions, sustainability policies, energy sector.